

Supporting Information to accompany:

Coordination networks assembled from $\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2$ and 4'-[4-(naphthalen-1-yl)phenyl]-3,2':6',3''-terpyridine: role of lattice solvents

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Figure S1. ESI (positive mode) mass spectrum of **1**.

Figure S2. ^1H NMR spectrum of **1** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Figure S3. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **1** (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Figure S4. HMQC spectrum of **1** (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_2 , 298 K).

Figure S5. HMBC spectrum of **1** (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_2 , 298 K).

Figure S6. IR spectrum of **1**.

Fig. S7. The *up/up/down/down* arrangement of 4-(naphthalen-1-yl)phenyl units around each rhombus in the (4,4) net in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Fig. S8. The structure of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Me}$ with solvent molecules omitted showing the void space (ca. 24%) accessible to solvent molecules; drawn using Mercury 2020.1, and calculated using a contact surface map using a probe radius of 1.2 Å.

Fig. S9. The structure of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Me}$: face-to-face π -interactions involving toluene molecules and the pyridine rings containing N2, and edge-to-face ($\text{C-H}\dots\pi$) contacts between the pyridine rings with N2 and N3 and toluene.

Fig. S10. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Fig. S11. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Me}$.

Fig. S12. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$ (cycle 2: after 48 hour exposure to CHCl_3 vapor). Green: temperature vs. time; blue: weight of sample vs. time; red: mass detection for m/z 83.0 (most intense peak), 85.0 and 87.0. The initial mass of sample was 1.69 mg and a weight loss of 0.28 mg corresponds to 16.6%.

Fig. S13. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CDCl}_3$ (cycle 3: after 24 hour exposure to CDCl_3 vapor). Green: temperature vs. time; blue: weight of sample vs. time; red: mass detection for m/z 84.0 (most intense peak), 86.0 and 88.0. The initial mass of sample was 1.59 mg and a weight loss of 0.25 mg corresponds to 15.7%.

Fig. S14. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (cycle 4: after 72 hours exposure to CH_2Cl_2 vapor). Green: temperature vs. time; blue: weight of sample vs. time; red: mass detection for m/z 49.0, 51.0, 84.0, 86.0.